

Effect of Interfacial Shear Strength on Mechanical Property of 4D

Carbon/Carbon Composites

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Abstract: In order to obtain effect of interfacial property on mechanical properties of 4D carbon/carbon composites, firstly, representative volume element is given; secondly, subprogram of periodic boundary conditions is compiled using periodic boundary conditions as theory basis; lastly, forecast research is carried out using homogenization theory and bilinear cohesive model about mechanical properties of 4D carbon/carbon composites. The 4D carbon/carbon composites have the following different interfacial shear strength 5.7MPa, 7.7MPa and 10.0MPa, respectively. As a result, average stiffness increases when interfacial shear strength increases, and axial elastic modulus is essentially in accord with experiment test result when the interfacial shear strength is 10.0MPa.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon/carbon composites is a kind of inorganic nonmetal matrix composites with the following excellent properties, such as low density, high specific strength and modulus, low coefficient of thermal expansion, etc. In present ,Carbon/carbon composites have been widely used in aerospace. As high temperature resistant material, it is used for solid rocket motor nozzles. As friction material, it is used for airplane brake. In the present work, carbon/carbon composites made by axial rod method consist of axial carbon rod , in-plane carbon fiber bundles, carbon matrix and interface, which have the following unique properties , such as high stiffness and strength in axial direction, good ablation resistance, and approximately isotropy in plane, etc.

Mechanical properties of carbon/carbon being influenced by carbon fiber , matrix and preform structure^[1] also rely on interfacial shear strength. Better mechanical properties can be achieved by interfacial shear strength design. In the condition of preform volume fraction being a constant, mechanical properties of 4D carbon/carbon composites made by axial rod method are researched when interfacial shear strength is 5.7MPa,7.7MPa and 10.0MPa,respectively. Change law are achieved between mechanical property and interfacial shear strength.

2 Basic theory

2.1 Bilinear cohesive model

In the present work, the interface of reinforcement and matrix is simulated by bilinear cohesive mode^[2-5], the behavior in elastic part can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} K_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_t \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \delta_s \\ \delta_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where t_n, t_s, t_t are normal and shear tractions respectively, K_n, K_s, K_t are normal and shear stiffness of interface respectively. In general, normal stiffness is from one to three times as large as shear stiffness of interface. In the present work, K_n is twice as large as K_s or K_t . $\delta_n, \delta_t, \delta_s$ are normal and shear displacements respectively.

The bilinear cohesive model is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Bilinear cohesive model

2.2 Homogenization

The relation of average stress and average strain in representative volume element is given as^[6]

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle &= \frac{1}{V_e} \int_{V_e} [C_{ijkl} - C_{ijmn} e_{mny}(\chi^{kl}(y))] dV_e \cdot \langle e_{ij} \rangle \\ &= C_{ijkl}^H \cdot \langle e_{ij} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$ and $\langle e_{ij} \rangle$ are average stress and average strain respectively, C_{ijkl}^H is the equivalent homogenized stiffness coefficients, χ^{kl} is the characteristic displacement tensor relating to mesoscale coordinate. e_{mny} is the strain tensor corresponding with χ^{kl} .

2.3 Periodic boundary conditions

The relation of average stress and average strain in the representative volume element can be concluded only if periodic boundary conditions are used in the representative volume element. Representative volume element is shown in Fig. 2. Periodic boundary conditions are that point, line and plane can satisfy different constraint equations respectively^[7-8].

Fig. 2 Representative volume element scheme

The relative displacements between the opposite faces of the representative volume element of dimension $2a \times 2b \times 2c$ are given together as follows

$$\begin{aligned} (u|_{x=a} - u|_{x=-a})|_{y,z} &= 2ae_{11} \\ (v|_{x=a} - v|_{x=-a})|_{y,z} &= 0 \\ (w|_{x=a} - w|_{x=-a})|_{y,z} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

abbreviated as $U_A - U_B = F_{AB}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (u|_{y=b} - u|_{y=-b})|_{y,z} &= 2be_{12} \\ (v|_{y=b} - v|_{y=-b})|_{y,z} &= 2be_{22} \\ (w|_{y=b} - w|_{y=-b})|_{y,z} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

abbreviated as $U_C - U_D = F_{CD}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (u|_{z=c} - u|_{z=-c})|_{x,y} &= 2ce_{13} \\ (v|_{z=c} - v|_{z=-c})|_{x,y} &= 2ce_{23} \\ (w|_{z=c} - w|_{z=-c})|_{x,y} &= 2ce_{33} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

abbreviated as $U_E - U_F = F_{EF}$.

In the above equations, u, v and w is the displacements in x, y and z direction

respectively, $e_{11}, e_{22}, e_{33}, e_{12}, e_{23}$ and e_{13} is pre-strain applied on representative volume

element, notation $|_{x=b}$ and $|_{x=-b}$ indicate the faces while $|_{y,z}$ indicates the common coordinates shared by the corresponding points on the pair of faces.

The displacement boundary conditions for representative volume element are given in Eq. (3) ~ (5). The equations are all independent for corresponding points on the pair of faces as indicated except the points along the edges of each face. As edges are shared by two faces, redundant conditions will arise if Eq. (3) ~ (5) are applied to faces including edges, causing compute error. An independent set of displacement boundary conditions for the edges can be obtained as follows

$$\begin{aligned} U_{II} - U_I &= F_{AB}, U_{III} - U_I = F_{AB} + F_{CD}, U_{IV} - U_I = F_{CD} \\ U_{VI} - U_V &= F_{AB}, U_{VII} - U_V = F_{AB} + F_{EF}, U_{VIII} - U_V = F_{EF} \\ U_X - U_{IX} &= F_{CD}, U_{XI} - U_{IX} = F_{CD} + F_{EF}, U_{XII} - U_{IX} = F_{EF} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Roman subscripts indicate the edges as shown in Fig. 2.

A set of independent and complete relations can be obtained for the 8 vertices as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} U_2 - U_1 &= F_{AB}, U_3 - U_1 = F_{AB} + F_{CD}, U_4 - U_1 = F_{CD} \\ U_5 - U_1 &= F_{AB} + F_{EF}, U_6 - U_1 = F_{AB} + F_{CD} + F_{EF}, \\ U_8 - U_1 &= F_{CD} + F_{EF} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where subscripts are the vertex numbers as shown in Fig. 2.

3 Representative volume element and material property

3.1 Representative volume element

In the condition of preform volume fraction being a constant, representative volume elements of 4D are constructed by analyzing their preform structures of carbon/carbon composites made by axial rod method as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig.3 Representative volume element of 4D carbon/carbon composites

3.2 Material property

The constituent properties of carbon/carbon composites are given in Table 1~3.

Table 1 Mechanical property of reinforcement phase

Axial E_{11}/GPa	modulus	Radial E_{22}/GPa	modulus	Shear modulus G_{12}/GPa
235		12.01		12.56
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}		Poisson's ratio ν_{13}		Poisson's ratio ν_{23}

0.376	0.376	0.404
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Table 2 Mechanical property of carbon matrix

Elastic E/GPa	Poisson's ratio
45.4	0.3

Table 3 Mechanical property of interface

Interface fracture energy/J.m ⁻²	Interface shear stiffness/N.mm ⁻³
123	1.0×10 ⁵

4 Finite element analysis

Subprogram of periodic boundary conditions is compiled using python language in ABAQUS. Periodic boundary conditions are applied on representative volume element of 4D carbon/carbon composites made by axial rod method when interfacial shear strength is 5.7MPa,7.7MPa and 10.0MPa,respectively. Average stiffness matrix and engineering elastic constant can be obtained by analyzing finite element analysis results. When interfacial shear strength is 5.7MPa,average stiffness matrix is given as(unit GPa)

$$[D]=\begin{bmatrix} 48.223 & 9.386 & 9.386 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 9.386 & 42.739 & 14.883 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 9.386 & 14.883 & 42.739 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 13.54 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.176 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.176 \end{bmatrix}$$

Engineering elastic constant is calculated using the foregoing average stiffness matrix. $E_1=45.25\text{GPa}, E_2=36.76\text{GPa}, E_3=36.76\text{GPa}, \nu_{21}=0.132, \nu_{12}=0.163, \nu_{31}=0.132, \nu_{13}=0.163, \nu_{23}=0.32, \nu_{32}=0.32, G_{23}=13.54\text{GPa}, G_{31}=4.17\text{GPa}, G_{12}=4.17\text{GPa}$.

When interfacial shear strength is 7.7MPa,average stiffness matrix is given as (unit GPa)

$$[D]=\begin{bmatrix} 50.901 & 10.101 & 10.101 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 10.101 & 44.653 & 15.515 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 10.101 & 15.515 & 44.653 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 13.71 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.391 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.391 \end{bmatrix}$$

Engineering elastic constant is calculated using the foregoing average stiffness matrix. $E_1=47.6\text{GPa}, E_2=38.3\text{GPa}, E_3=38.3\text{GPa}, \nu_{21}=0.134, \nu_{12}=0.167, \nu_{31}=0.134, \nu_{13}=0.167, \nu_{23}=0.318, \nu_{32}=0.318, G_{23}=13.71\text{GPa}, G_{31}=4.39\text{GPa}, G_{12}=4.39\text{GPa}$.

When interfacial shear strength is 10.0MPa,average stiffness matrix is given as (unit GPa)

$$[D]=\begin{bmatrix} 53.320 & 10.429 & 10.429 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 10.429 & 45.623 & 15.783 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 10.429 & 15.783 & 45.623 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 13.89 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.632 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.632 \end{bmatrix}$$

Engineering elastic constant is calculated using the foregoing average stiffness matrix. $E_1=49.8\text{GPa}, E_2=39.2\text{GPa}, E_3=39.2\text{GPa}, v_{21}=0.13, v_{12}=0.17, v_{31}=0.13, v_{13}=0.17$, $v_{23}=0.31$, $v_{32}=0.31$, $G_{23}=13.89\text{GPa}$, $G_{31}=4.63\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=4.63\text{GPa}$.

The results of engineering elastic constant are listed in Table 4.

Table 4 Mechanical properties of carbon/carbon composites with different preform structure

Engineering constant	elastic	5.7MPa	7.7MPa	10.0MPa
E_1/GPa		45.25	47.6	49.8
E_2/GPa		36.76	38.3	39.2
E_3/GPa		36.76	38.3	39.2
v_{21}		0.132	0.134	0.13
v_{12}		0.163	0.167	0.17
v_{31}		0.132	0.134	0.13
v_{13}		0.163	0.167	0.17
v_{23}		0.32	0.318	0.31
v_{32}		0.32	0.318	0.31
G_{23}/GPa		13.54	13.71	13.89
G_{31}/GPa		4.17	4.39	4.63
G_{12}/GPa		4.17	4.39	4.63

The Table 4 shows that average stiffness increases when interfacial shear strength increases.

The above computing result and experiment result are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Comparison of theory and experiment result for 4D carbon/carbon composites

Item	Axial modulus /GPa
experiment	52.1
interfacial shear strength 5.7MPa	computing result 45.25
	error 13.1%
interfacial shear strength 7.7MPa	computing result 47.60
	error 8.6%
interfacial shear strength 10MPa	computing result 49.80
	error 4.4%

The Table 5 shows that axial elastic modulus is essentially in accord with experiment test

result when the interfacial shear strength is 10.0MPa.

5 Conclusions

By computing and analyzing, the several results are given:

(1) Average stiffness increases when interfacial shear strength increases for 4D carbon/carbon composites;

(2) Axial elastic modulus is essentially in accord with experiment test result when the interfacial shear strength is 10.0MPa;

(3) Mechanical property design can be realized rapidly using homogenization theory.

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